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CONCEPT CONFIGURATION OF THE DISCURSIVE APPROACH OF THE LITERARY TEXT

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The article addresses the issue of defining the concept of the discursive approach of the literary text. At the same time, it highlights the necessity and topicality of the discursive approach of the literary text which can be seen as an optimal way of textual analysis aiming at the integration of all the components of the communicative competence. In this regard, the discursive approach requires an extension of the text reception focusing on the socio-cultural and pragmatic dimensions. The study presents some theoretical models of discursive practices that favour the discursive approach of the literary text as well.

Keywords: literary text, approach, discourse, configuration, pragmatics, discursive practice.

CONFIGURAȚIA CONCEPTULUI DE ABORDARE DISCURSIVĂ A TEXTULUI LITERAR

În articol este abordată problematica privind definirea conceptului de abordare discursivă a textului literar. Totodată, este evidențiată necesitatea și actualitatea abordării discursive a textului literar care poate fi definită ca o modalitate optimă de analiză textuală vizând integrarea tuturor componentelor competenței de comunicare. În acest sens, abordarea discursivă impune o extindere a receptării textului, focusându-se pe dimensiunea socioculturală și pragmatică. Studiul prezintă, de asemenea, câteva modele teoretice ale unor practici discursive care încurajează abordarea discursivă a textului literar.

Cuvinte-cheie: text literar, abordare, discurs, configurație, pragmatică, practică discursivă.

Given the fact that the knowledge related to the structural linguistic norms and the ability to use it in different social contexts are no longer actual and sufficient for developing the communicative competence, the analysis of a literary text through the discursive approach brings a new breath in the study of the English language and literature. With this in mind, it increasingly emphasizes its significance and topicality in the field. It supposes the integration of all the components of the communicative competence into the process of learning/teaching English as it has been proved that the communicative competence generates multi-aspectual complexity and difficulty in being developed [1].

According to the Romanian linguist Eugeniu Coșeriu [2], during the communicative act, the speaker uses not only the linguistic system, but also a prior knowledge of facts, images, contextual situations, ideas formed in connection with the things involved in the communication.

Relating the language to the surrounding reality, we can underline its goal and social impact. Thus, the compositional model proposed by the European Commission emphasizes the importance of two other significant components of the communicative competence: *pragmatic and socio-linguistic competences*.

These two competences, as reported by Ch. Savignon, imply the knowledge and understanding of the social framework in which the language is used. It is very important to know the relation between those who interact in the communicative act, in particular, the status and role of these participants, the form and purpose of this interaction. Only under these circumstances we can deduce the meaning of the speaker's message [3].

In this light, the pragmatic importance and the role of the socio-linguistic competence become indisputable. This idea finds a basis in Dell Hymes' opinion that the acquisition of a foreign language requires especially sociolinguistic knowledge for an efficient communication, regardless of the quality of linguistic knowledge [4]. In fact, the social (extralinguistic) and linguistic practice complement each other and follow the process of fixing and strengthening the relations of societal power through language [5]. Since the literary text is the expression of the language, we can learn the social norms through the text unless we use the appropriate approach.

Further, we present some models of the discursive practices which directly favour the discursive approach of the literary text.

Table

Models of discursive practices

Author	Models of discursive practices
<i>Teun A. van Dijk</i>	The Dutch researcher Teun A. van Dijk approaches the analysis of discourse by combining cognitive theories with social and linguistic ones. In this approach in three levels - discursive, cognitive and social, the researcher places cognition at the intermediate level. The incorporation of a cognitive study allows the scientists to perceive the way of a broader consolidation of the social phenomenon through everyday popular discourse. There are some objections to the respective practice related to the weaker orientation towards transformation, the approach being more focused on reproducing ideologies.
<i>Dominique Maingueneau</i>	Dominique Maingueneau studies the specificity of the literary fact that is related to its conditions of production. The researcher states that the text cannot be dissociated from its context. The author analyses the relationship of the literary work with its production context and, at the same time, the relations between subjectivity, the literary institution and the textual functioning.
<i>J.L. Austin</i>	The theory of speech acts is produced by the researcher J.L. Austin. Language, according to his theory, needs to be considered as an activity, rather than a series of <i>acotextual</i> and abstract utterances. The researcher distinguishes in the act of speaking a <i>locutionary</i> aspect (when you speak/refer to something), <i>illocutionary</i> aspect (what you do when you say something) and a <i>perlocutionary</i> aspect (the action done by saying something). The analysis of the context in which we use certain expressions and phrases is the researcher's basic method [6].
<i>Norman Fairclough</i>	Norman Fairclough's method encourages the discourse approach by advancing a three-dimensional framework, aiming at establishing three different modes of analysis separated from each other: analysis of linguistic texts (production, transmission and reception of the text), analysis of discursive facts as instances of socio-cultural practice and analysis of discourse practice. Thus, the researcher is concerned with the ways of discursive modelling of social practices and their discursive impact [7].

According to the theory above, Fairclough emphasizes the need to explain the connection between social, historical and cultural conditions in the process of text analysis. The study of the relations between the socio-cultural practice and the language used is supported by the social and cultural theory [8].

The three-dimensional model is represented in Fig.1

Fig.1. N. Fairclough's three-dimensional model.

In the light of the graph above, we highlight the value and efficiency of Fairclough’s three-dimensional perspective in the development of the discursive analysis of a literary text.

As a result of the dependence of literature on the socio-economic development and, in the same time, of its independence, the words get several meanings in a certain literary context. In literature, the linguistic patterns are not used only to render the message or point out some visions, some beliefs, attitudes, on the contrary, the words are used to describe the reality with a view to change it.

Keeping that in mind, the literary text points out its actional aspect which transforms it into a discourse. The text analysis which involves the socio-cultural elements is focused on the analysis of its *internal structures*, for example, the plot, setting, characters, composition, logical parts, themes, language, *as well as the external structures* of the text, namely, the historical, political, social contexts.

The analysis of literary texts takes a new form with the researches made by the French linguist Benveniste [9]. He proposes new approaches in text didactics, especially, ways of working on the text taking into consideration its production conditions.

Therefore, the discursive approach is a new direction of text research, which borrows only the methodological tools from other approaches, but with different investigation objectives. Hence, the discursive approach of the text underlines and studies the social problems which are rendered in the text under different levels: syntactic, semantic, narrative. As a matter of fact, the text comprises the society in its structure, values, attitudes and motifs [10].

In this way we would like to underline that the literary text represents a set of authors’ assumptions and not just a source of information. In the process of the text analysis, the learners aim not only to study the linguistic material, to make the plot or the stylistic analyses, they have to extend the study of the text in order to understand those assumptions.

According to M. Bakhtin, the text is a complex fact, a place where a series of heterogeneous discourses intersect. As the discourse relates to the society or community, the history and society should be an integrant part of the analysis process [11].

Discourse relates to interactivity and institutional character of language which focuses on the understanding of the text codes. In this regard, pragmatics provides various analysis tools. According to the French pragmatist Dominique Maingueneau, literary pragmatics generates numerous possibilities to exploit new textual valences [12].

Thus, we might say that literary texts are means of transmitting culture. They provide the learner with other cultures through the language, through the events that occurred in the texts. The texts teach the reader to follow some models of behaviour, rules, thinking and ideologies. In this way, we can see that the literary text isn’t independent; it is related to the social activities which valorise its opportunities to communicate in time. It builds the image of a certain society. The discursive activity implies the indirect interaction, namely, the unspoken content, as well as the ways of understanding the text by the reader. This kind of interaction makes the text more dynamic and transforms it into a living discourse tested in time by mentalities, attitudes, interactions [13].

Consequently, we can establish three factors aiming the text relation with its context: *social context, communication situation, cognitive and dynamic aspect of the verbal communication* [14].

According to the researcher J.-B. Grize, the discursive activity takes place at a certain time, in a certain place and has a certain purpose. The author states that the discursive activity itself generates the production of the communication situation. He underlines the idea that the circumstances in which the discourse is produced have a great impact on the form and content of the text. In other words, we deal with a dialectic dependence between the discursive activity and communication situation [15].

The relation of the text with its context, *id est* the implicit of the text with its explicit part is rendered as well by the formula *text-iceberg* of Carmen Vlad: the phrase covers the text together with its context [16]. Speaking about the explicit we mean the total set of verbal signs which make the text, while the implicit is represented by the unspoken of the text which we call the context of the text.

At the end of the study, we would like to mention that the objective of the discursive approach of the text is not to analyse a treasure, it is, among other things, to make the learner understand the construction and role of this treasure in the practices of discourse.

From this point of view, we propose schematically and semantically the concept configuration of the discursive approach of the literary text (Fig.2).

Fig.2. Concept configuration of the discursive approach of the literary text (author Tatiana Lașcu).

Conclusions

As a result of the synthesis of the previously studied theoretical foundations we can define the concept of *discursive approach* as a new direction in the text didactics, it is a new modality of the literary text analysis seen as discourse by studying the facts from the reality conditioned by the context (conditions of text production), by the interaction between sender (narrator) message/code and receiver (reader) through the situation of communication and discursive activity that transposes the receiver beyond the text.

Taking this into account, the text is seen not as an independent structure, but as a structure related to a sociocultural activity, through which it can transmit values, behaviour, ideologies or rules set in the respective society.

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